

Studies on Thorium Tungstate Ion-exchanger

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In continuation of our work^{1,2} with insoluble tungstates, presently we have synthesised a granular variety of thorium tungstate (TT) suitable for column operation, prepared for the first time by Turnov and Kovba³. The preparation, properties and ion-exchange behaviour of crystalline variety of TT have also been studied by Qureshi and Nabi⁴ and De and Chowdhury⁵. The present work describes the exchange capacities and distribution coefficients of several cations on the granular variety of TT and useful separation of some binary mixtures of cations.

Results and Discussion

During the preparation of TT, pH of the reaction condition had negligible effect on the exchange capacity and also on the exchanger (Table 1).

TABLE 1—CONDITION OF SYNTHESIS AND A FEW PROPERTIES OF THORIUM TUNGSTATE

Sample no.	Concn. of reagents (M)		pH	Ion-exchange capacity for Na ⁺ /meq/g		Th : W ratio
	TN*	SW*		for Na ⁺ /meq/g		
				40°	80°	
1.	0.10	0.10	1	0.06	0.12	1 : 1.7
2.	0.10	0.10	2	0.10	0.20	1 : 1.8
3.	0.10	0.10	3	0.08	0.15	1 : 1.75
4.	0.10	0.10	4	0.05	0.10	1 : 1.7

*TN=thorium nitrate ; SW=sodium tungstate.

However, sample no. 2 has not only the highest ion-exchange capacity but also granular quality making it possible to use in column separations. Other products obtained were in very powdery form. Automatically, sample no. 2 was chosen for further studies. Thermal analysis of the sample shows that there is an initial loss of water near 100° corresponding to a broad endothermic peak, and also there is a small endothermic peak at 476° which may be due to the condensation of tungstate groups. A small exothermic peak at 633° is perhaps due to the formation of oxides. There is negligible loss of weight at about 450°. Ir spectra reveal similar features to those reported by earlier workers⁵. The pH-titration curve indicates a single break, corresponding to a monofunctional acid grouping.

The ion-exchange capacity of TT increased (K⁺ > Na⁺ > Li⁺) with decrease in hydrated radii of the exchanging alkali metal ions and alkaline earths cations (Table 2). Due to moderate heating, the exchange capacity increased with temperature (Table 1), probably due to loss in weight for the

TABLE 2—ION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF THORIUM TUNGSTATE

Metal ion	Hydrated radius Å	Ion-exchange capacity
Li ⁺	3.40	0.07
Na ⁺	2.76	0.10
K ⁺	2.32	0.12
Mg ²⁺	7.00	0.085
Ca ²⁺	6.80	0.09
Ba ²⁺	5.90	0.12

elimination of water. Radiation dose upto 50 M rad on the sample had no effect with respect to their exchange capacities. The compounds was found to be highly stable in different chemical environments, only a little amount of tungsten being released in the solution even with the treatment with 4 M mineral acids or 2 M alkalis. Moreover, it is found to be stable in solutions of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, CaCl₂ and BaCl₂ and also in alcohol and benzene.

The values of K_D of several cations at different pH show that the adsorption of a cation is relatively more at higher pH. However, the trend is quite different from the earlier results and difficult separations could be achieved (Table 3). The principles of these separations are based on the high K_D values of Bi^{III}, Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} respectively in comparison to the other metal ions involved in these binary mixtures.

TABLE 3—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF METAL IONS ON THORIUM TUNGSTATE COLUMNS*

Sl. no.	Separation achieved	Metal ions taken (µg)	Eluent
1.	Bi ³⁺ -(Pb ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Al ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺)	Pb ²⁺ (2776.6) Fe ²⁺ (720.2) Al ³⁺ (446.2) Cu ²⁺ (1239) Zn ²⁺ (779) Cd ²⁺ (1236.4) Hg ²⁺ (2106.3) Bi ³⁺ (1864.3)	Pb ²⁺ , water ^a Fe ²⁺ , water ^a Al ³⁺ , water ^a Cu ²⁺ , water ^a Zn ²⁺ , water ^a Cd ²⁺ , water ^a Hg ²⁺ , water ^a Bi ³⁺ ; 2M HNO ₃
2.	Ti ⁴⁺ -(VO ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Al ³⁺)	VO ²⁺ (546.4) Fe ²⁺ (720.2) Al ³⁺ (446.2) Ti ⁴⁺ (361.2)	VO ²⁺ ; water ^b Fe ²⁺ ; water ^b Al ³⁺ ; water ^a Ti ⁴⁺ ; 2M H ₂ SO ₄
3.	Zr ⁴⁺ -(UO ₂ ²⁺ , Ce ⁴⁺)	UO ₂ ²⁺ (201.4) Ce ⁴⁺ (196.8) Zr ⁴⁺ (225.2)	UO ₂ ²⁺ ; water ^a Ce ⁴⁺ ; water ^b Zr ⁴⁺ ; 2M HCl

*Exchanger used in column=5 g. ^apH=2. ^bpH=1.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A. R. grade. A Sambros 335 pH meter was used for pH measure-